

Bijlia dilatata
Clay Prince Albert vygie

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 3-5 cm high, about 10 cm in diameter

Distribution:

Endemic to a single valley in the Western Cape and restricted to disjunct sites on quartzite pavements.

Importance:

The Red List of Southern African Plants notes that the species is range-restricted species (EOO 260 km²) and 'declining due to ongoing habitat loss and degradation'. A recent publication by Milton et al. (2024) studied eight populations and concluded that grazing and climate change appear to be contributing to declines in this endemic habitat specific dwarf succulent, already threatened by land transformation and poaching in the Succulent Karoo hotspot of South Africa.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 41.67 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.91 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.75 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 95.8%, Duplicated: 3.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 65 443.77 kilobases

Contig number: 1 590

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